

Detecting Denial of Wallet Attacks in Serverless Computing: A Neural ODE-LTC Approach

Deepanjan Mitra

Dept. of Computer Science & Engg.
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
ORCID: 0000-0003-4888-7782

Nabendu Chaki

Dept. of Computer Science & Engg.
University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
ORCID: 0000-0003-3242-680X

Monowar Bhuyan

Dept. of Computing Science
Umeå University, SE-90187, Sweden
ORCID: 0000-0002-9842-7840

Abstract—The serverless Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) paradigm offers a fine granularity for the pay-per-use billing model, where users are charged based on the actual function execution time and do not have to pay for idle resources. Thereby, FaaS in a serverless environment brings the promise that it completely abstracts infrastructure management. This allows the developers to focus solely on application development. On the other hand, the serverless applications, being deployed as a dense web of FaaS artifacts, increase the attack surface. This makes the FaaS paradigm susceptible to financial exhaustion attacks, also known as Denial of Wallet (DoW), where the attacker attempts to inflate the usage bill by illegitimate escalation of resource consumption. This paper proposes a robust detection method for DoW attacks on the serverless platform using the Neural Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) with a Liquid Time Constant (LTC). The experiments, conducted on a benchmark dataset, represent real-world attack scenarios, compared with baseline methods. The proposed method outperforms the baselines for multiple evaluation metrics, proving its effectiveness in precision-critical scenarios.

Index Terms—Serverless Computing, FaaS, Economic DDoS, Denial of Wallet, Financial Exhaustion Attack, Neural ODE

I. INTRODUCTION

The term “serverless” refers to the fact that infrastructure management is abstracted from the developers so that they can solely focus on writing code. The notion that computing will one day be used as a paid utility is quite old [1]. On serverless, it is achieved by using the Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) paradigm. In traditional cloud computing, the rented resources are often under-utilized for applications with sporadic usage patterns. Serverless offers a finer granularity pay-per-use model. The users are billed for the actual execution time and resources consumed by the serverless functions without the need to pay for idle resources. In addition, the level of infrastructure management by developers is significantly reduced, allowing them to focus solely on deploying serverless functions. Like any computing utility, the serverless pay-as-you-go billing model is accompanied by the crony evil known as Denial of Wallet (DoW) attacks [3]. In serverless, applications are deployed as small functions, with intricate interdependencies, that execute in response to a myriad variety of events and triggers. This introduces a vector of potential entry points, increasing the attack surface. Moreover, the rise of stealthiness in attack strategy often results in false attack detections. This occurs due to the lack of precise modeling

of system dynamics. This work proposes an approach for serverless systems that employs Neural Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) with Liquid Time Constant (LTC) [15] to model the dynamics of a serverless system for DoW attack detection. The proposed solution is capable of detecting attacks with high precision compared to the existing approaches.

A. Denial of Wallet Attack in Serverless Computing

Denial of Wallet (DoW) [3] is a financial exhaustion attack which involves attackers inflating the usage bill of a cloud user by illegitimate escalation of the users’ resource consumption. This is achieved using various methods, the most popular among them being the Economic Distributed Denial of Service (EDDoS) attacks. These attacks pose unique challenges for serverless applications for the following reasons:

- 1) Serverless frameworks offer a finer level of granularity by leveraging applications in terms of functions. Unlike cloud computing, where an attacker needs to generate sustained high load to significantly impact the users’ bill, in serverless, even short bursts of numerous invocations can lead to substantial cost escalations affecting the economic sustainability of users.
- 2) Unlike conventional cloud infrastructure, where attackers likely target a cluster or a Virtual Machine (VM), in serverless, attackers can disperse their target over a range of specific functions. Thus, the increased attack surface often reduces the palpability of the attack, leading to late recognition.
- 3) In the traditional cloud, auto-scaling takes time as it generally involves bringing up a new VM as an additional unit of computation. Whereas the serverless platforms, leveraging lightweight functions, are designed to scale instantly. This allows an attacker to quickly trigger a massive scaling event, driving up costs.

Figure 1 presents a schematic diagram of serverless architecture and shows how attackers escalate function execution, mimicking legitimate traffic and leading to increased costs. In many cases, the attack occurrences are not disclosed as the providers fear that the news may cause them to lose customers, entailing financial loss.

B. Contributions

The contributions of this work are listed below:

Fig. 1: Serverless architecture and the effects of DoW attacks

- 1) Developed a novel scheme for detecting DoW attacks in serverless computing environments.
- 2) Demonstrated the highly precise detection of Denial-of-Wallet (DoW) attacks through continuous modeling of system dynamics utilizing a Neural Ordinary Differential Equation (Neural ODE) with Liquid Time-Constant (LTC) networks, thereby ensuring reliable and accurate identification of malicious activities.
- 3) Compared the proposed solution with the LSTM variants, empirically demonstrating that the proposed approach achieves superior performance, particularly by minimizing false positives.

II. RELATED WORK

The DoW attacks become crucial when users are penalized with additional costs without using the resources from the providers. We summarized the following existing works [3]–[9]. Kelly et al. [3] introduce how DoW attacks bypass the serverless systems, but the attack analysis limits itself to theoretically, whereas Shen et al. [4] performed DoW attack to a serverless platform that co-locates malicious functions for slowing down the target functions. However, the detection strategy faces limitations due to its underlying assumptions of a linear relationship between workloads and performance metrics which often doesn’t hold true in complex systems.

In [5], the authors defined three DoW attacks, such as blast distributed DoW (high-rate), continual inconspicuous DDoW (low-rate), and chained DDoW (combined) attacks that target URL of a “serverless service” in a short period of time, which escalate the usage bill of the target serverless users without being noticed, but lacks detection methods. A prototype for financial attack execution is proposed in [6], where three potential synthetic attack vectors modeled, namely constant rate, exponential rate and random rate attacks, used them for validation. They are yet to be assessed for applicability to serverless computing. Similarly, DoW attack dataset for serverless environments is proposed at [8]. Kelly et al. [7] present a method of using heat maps to represent serverless traffic and then training an image-classification algorithm to distinguish between normal and malicious behavior. Despite

its high accuracy in detecting attacks, the method’s need for extensive historical data makes it impractical for rapid or data-limited scenarios. Furthermore, its offline nature and high computational cost for real-time analysis render it unsuitable for online attack detection. Shimol et al. [9] detect compromised serverless functions by identifying post-exploitation abnormal behavior on serverless functions, which is a passive detection strategy that causes financial loss. Recently, Renukadevi et al. [10] proposed a Deep Wavelet Neural Networks approach for DoW attack detection. However, wavelet transforms are computationally intensive for large or high-dimensional data. Furthermore, Deep Wavelet Neural Networks primarily extract features using wavelet decomposition and nonlinearities, lacking explicit continuous-time modelling.

Table I compares and illustrates the significance of the proposed work with SOTA methods. The state of the art mechanisms mostly employ sequential modelling techniques, such as LSTM [11], [12] and GRU [13]. Deep learning-based sequential models are either gated or non-gated mechanisms. However, gated mechanisms are computationally intensive and fail to model the nascent continuous system dynamics. Hence, the proposed non-gated Neural ODE-LTC approach performs well with fewer model parameters than gated neural networks.

TABLE I: Comparison among prior works

Reference	Dataset (T/B) [†]	DoWD*	Continuous-Time Dynamics	Parameter Efficiency
[3], 2021	T	✗	N/A	N/A
[4], 2022	T	✓	✗	✗
[5], 2022	T	✗	N/A	N/A
[6], 2023	T	✗	N/A	N/A
[7], 2024	T	✓	✗	✗
[8], 2024	B	✗	N/A	N/A
[9], 2025	T	✓	✗	✗
[10], 2025	T	✓	✗	✗
Proposed Work, 2025	B	✓	✓	✓

[†] - T: Testbed; B: Benchmark Dataset, * - DoW Attack Detection.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section starts by enumerating the problem statement and providing a description of the proposed detection method to uncover DoW attacks.

A. Problem Formulation

There is a lack of effective attack detection schemes due to the stealthy nature of the attack. Further, current detection schemes concentrate on large amounts of historical data for attack detection. The state-of-the-art detection schemes fail to model the system dynamics closely, leading to a discrete approximation instead of a continuous one. This often results in attack detection schemes falsely classifying benign system states as potential attack instances, which hinders the service of legitimate requests, leading to denial of service. With the increasing stealthiness of attack trajectories and increased fluctuations in the nature of attacks, it is imperative to understand the attack patterns in short periods of history and be able to detect them as soon as possible to avoid financial losses.

Let $D = \{(x_i, y_i) | x_i \in X, y_i \in Y\}_{i=1}^N$ denote the dataset of size N , where X are the input features and Y is the dependent output. Each sample (x_i, y_i) consists of $X_i \in R^d$ a d dimensional vector of features recorded from the workflow of serverless functions during attack and as well as in normal circumstances and $y_i = \{0, 1\}$, where $y_i = 1$ denotes the positive class, i.e., an attack, and $y_i = 0$ denotes negative class, i.e., benign or normal. The goal is to train a model $f_\epsilon : R^d \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ that maps each input x_i to a predicted class label, $\hat{y}_i = f_\epsilon(x_i)$ where ϵ is the criterion that measures the performance of f_ϵ . In this work, ϵ denotes accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score performance measures.

Fig. 2: Framework for financial attack detection using neural ODE (LTC)

B. The Neural-ODE (LTC) model

The Neural Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) [14] is an emerging alternative to traditional discrete-layered deep neural networks. Unlike traditional neural networks, where the transformation of the input to the output is considered as a sequence of discrete transformations of the hidden states, the Neural ODE treats this transformation as a continuous process. It achieves this by modeling the transformation of the hidden state of the dynamic system as an Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE). In a traditional neural network, the transformation of the hidden state is usually described by equation 1, where f is a neural network with parameter θ . On the other hand, the Neural ODEs model uses the differential equation 2, where $x(t)$ represents the hidden state at time t and f is the function approximated by the neural network which defines the evolution of the hidden state over time.

$$x(t+1) = x(t) + f(x(t), I(t), t, \theta) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d(x(t))}{dt} = f(x(t), I(t), t, \theta) \quad (2)$$

Similar to its biological inspirational counterpart, the Neural ODE consists of sensory, motor, command and inter-neurons. The sensory neurons interacting with the environment correspond to neurons ingesting input features. Similar to neurons transmitting action signals, the motor neurons correspond to the output layer that generate predictions. The command neuron temporally steers the dynamic state of the model and

the inter-neurons act as mediators between the sensory and motor neurons.

The Neural ODEs were found to lack stability. To overcome this limitation, Hasani et al. [15] integrated the concept of liquid time constants into the model, extending the idea conceived by Nakamura et al. [16]. In [15], the dynamics of the system is modeled as “networks of linear first-order dynamical systems modulated via nonlinear interlinked gates” resulting in liquid time constants “coupled to their hidden state, with outputs being computed by numerical differential equation solvers”. In LTC-based Neural ODE, the dynamics of the hidden state of the network is given by the differential Equation 3.

$$\frac{d(x(t))}{dt} = -\frac{x(t)}{\tau} + f(x(t), I(t), t, \theta)(A - x(t)) \quad (3)$$

From the Equation 3, it is evident that the time constant $\tau_{ltc} = \frac{\tau}{1 + \tau f(x(t), I(t), t, \theta)}$ is dependent on the input $I(t)$ and varies with time t and helps enforce stability and equilibrium (liquidity) in the model.

C. Overall Solution Framework

The workflow of the proposed solution, illustrated in figure 2, consists of two key blocks: block A and block B. These blocks delineate the training and testing phases of the Neural ODE (LTC) model for DoW attack detection. Block A corresponds to the training phase of the model on the dataset [8], while Block B represents the evaluation of the trained model on unseen test data. Algorithm 1 describes the training process of the Neural ODE (LTC) model M_{ODE} using the training dataset D_{train} . Each input instance (x_t, y_t) in dataset D corresponds to a state of the serverless system. x_t denotes a set of system features recorded at time instants t across various levels of the serverless stack under both benign and attack conditions. y_t is the ground truth corresponding to each x_t , which can assume a value of 1 or 0, indicating the presence and absence of an attack, respectively. Before training, the model M_{ODE} is initialized with the number of sensory and motor neurons and the learning rate. During training, each system instance x_t in D_{train} is encoded into a latent representation. The ODE solver then computes the trajectory, which is then passed through the output layer to compute the predicted label \hat{y}_t . The binary cross-entropy loss between the predicted label \hat{y}_t and the true label y_t is optimized. Ultimately, the trained Neural ODE (LTC) model M_{ODE}^T is obtained, along with the predicted labels \hat{y}_t for the training dataset. Algorithm 2 corresponding to Figure 2 block B describes the testing and evaluation procedure for the trained model M_{ODE}^T on unseen data D_{test} . The performance of attack detection is evaluated using the metrics accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Dataset

The dataset [8] comprises a rich collection of features representing system behaviors and function invocations. The Table

Algorithm 1 Training the Neural ODE (LTC) model

Input: Training data D_{train} , Neural ODE (LTC) model M_{ODE} , Dense output layer $Dense$, Differential equation solver $ODE\text{-Solver}$

Output: The trained Neural ODE (LTC) model and the predicted label \hat{y}_t for each instance $(x_t, y_t) \in D_{\text{train}}$.

- 1: **Define Neural ODE model:** Design the system of differential equations parameterized by M_{ODE} and initialize parameters θ , which includes the number of sensory, motor neurons and the learning rate.
 - 2: **Train Neural ODE model:**
 - 3: **for** each instance in D_{train} **do**
 - 4: Encode the input into a latent representation $z(t)$ using $f(z(t), \theta)$.
 - 5: Solve the ODE using $ODE\text{-Solver}(z, f_\theta, t)$ to obtain trajectory $z(t)$.
 - 6: Pass $z(t)$ through $Dense$ to compute the predicted label \hat{y}_t .
 - 7: Optimize the loss function (binary cross-entropy) between \hat{y}_t and the true label y_t .
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **Return** The Neural ODE (LTC) M_{ODE}^T model trained on data D_{train} .
-

Algorithm 2 Proposed Attack Detection

Input: Test data D_{test} , the trained Neural ODE (LTC) model M_{ODE}^T , Dense output layer $Dense$, Differential equation solver $ODE\text{-Solver}$

Output: Predicted label \hat{y}_t for each instance $(x_t, y_t) \in D_{\text{test}}$ and performance metrics - accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score.

- 1: **Evaluate on test data:**
 - 2: **for** each instance in D_{test} **do**
 - 3: Use the model M_{ODE}^T to compute the latent representation $z(t)$.
 - 4: Pass $z(t)$ through the trained model M_{ODE}^T 's dense output layer $Dense$ to compute the predicted label \hat{y}_t .
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: **Attack detection:**
 - 7: **for** each instance $(x_t, y_t) \in D_{\text{test}}$ **do**
 - 8: **if** $\hat{y}_t = y_t$ and $y_t = 1$ **then**
 - 9: **Print** a message raising an alarm: "The system is under DoW attack".
 - 10: **else**
 - 11: **Print** "The system is not under attack".
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end for**
-

It presents the various features of the dataset [8] categorized across different levels of the serverless framework. The target feature in the dataset [8], "bot", is binary, where 0 denotes benign traffic and 1 indicates attack instances.

TABLE II: Dataset [8] features across different levels of the serverless stack

Architectural Level	Features
Function level	FunctionID, FunctionTrigger, InvocationDelay, ResponseDelay, FunctionDuration, ActiveFunctionsAtRequest, ActiveFunctionsAtResponse
VM level	vmcategory, vmcorecountbucket, vmmemorybucket
System level	avgcpu, p95maxcpu, maxcpu
Network level	IP, Round Trip Time (RTT)

B. Attack Scenario

DoW attacks in the serverless model are an emerging field of research, although an extensive study of the same has been conducted in cloud environments. Kelly et al. [7] provide a classification of attacks into random rate, geometric rate and linear rate attacks. In random rate attacks, the traffic volume is chosen by the attacker randomly in each time step. These attack patterns can be learnt by efficient sequential model algorithms. The geometric rate attack involves the number of attack requests getting multiplied, causing it to grow exponentially. These attacks are relatively easy to detect owing to stark temporal increase in traffic volume. In linear rate attacks, the attacker keeps the request rate constant for a long period, increasing the number very slowly at long intervals of time. These attacks are very hard to detect as the traffic volume remains close to benign traffic, and their changes are long-term. The attacker mimics legitimate usage patterns, making it difficult to distinguish.

C. Experimental Setup

Two variants of the Neural ODE (LTC) model have been used, containing 18 and 36 command neurons, respectively. There is one motor neuron corresponding to the target variable. The number of sensory neurons is equal to the number of features, which is 18 in our case. All experiments were run on the dataset, and the performance metrics were recorded, taking an average of over 20 experimental runs. The results of our experiments are summarized in Table III. We further compare our proposed method against the baseline Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model [11] with its vanilla and attention mechanism [12] variants. For the LSTM models, we used 400 epochs and a batch size of 64. In addition, we employed two variants with the LSTM layer having 18 and 36 nodes, respectively, employing ADAM [17] as the optimizer and 'binary-cross entropy' for the loss function. The performance of the model is evaluated using the metrics accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which quantify different aspects of its attack prediction ability.

D. Results and Discussion

Neural ODE (LTC), for both configurations achieves extremely high accuracy i.e., 99.73% for 18 neurons and 99.90%

TABLE III: Performance comparison among baseline models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Neural ODE(LTC)(18,1)	0.9973	0.9851	1.0000	0.9916
Neural ODE(LTC)(36,1)	0.9990	0.9936	1.0000	0.9967
LSTM 18-units	0.8477	0.5379	1.0000	0.6805
LSTM 36-units	0.9629	0.7893	1.0000	0.8823
LSTM attention 18-units	0.9697	0.8774	0.8978	0.8519
LSTM attention 36-units	0.9986	0.9642	0.8609	0.9832

for 36 neurons. This indicates that the model is highly effective in capturing underlying temporal patterns. The increase in accuracy, although marginal, from 18 to 36 units, indicates that adding more neurons enhances the model’s ability to generalize. Both configurations attain perfect recall of 1.0. This means that the model successfully identifies all the positive instances. On the other hand the precision is also exceptionally high for both configurations. The model with 18 neurons achieves a precision of 98.51% and a precision of 99.36% with 36 neurons. This increase indicates that the model becomes better at reducing false positive instances with more neurons. The F1-score improves from 0.9916 with 18 neurons to 0.9967 with 36 neurons, suggesting that the addition of neurons makes the model slightly more effective in achieving a more balanced performance.

1) *Comparison with SOTA methods:* There is dearth of published works involving detection of DoW attacks in the serverless. In fact, to the best of our findings, this article is the first work that uses Neural ODE (LTC) for the detection of attacks in a serverless setup. Hence, it remains beyond the scope of this work to perform a comparative study with other approaches that might be using Neural ODE to address the issue of DoW attacks. The existing works require a large amount of historical data spanning across several months. Therefore we compare the proposed method with baseline time-series based deep learning models like vanilla LSTM [11] and LSTM with attention [12]. Starting with accuracy, Neural ODE (LTC) models exhibit superior performance, reaching almost 99.90% accuracy with the 36-unit configuration. This exceptional accuracy highlights their ability to consistently identify both positive and negative instances, making them especially valuable in scenarios where any misclassifications can prove costly. Although the LSTM model with attention also achieves near-perfect accuracy, the Neural ODE model maintains an edge in delivering consistent results across different configurations. In terms of precision, Neural ODE models again show a clear advantage. The 36-unit Neural ODE (LTC) models exhibit higher precision levels compared to the LSTM model variants, with the former achieving a precision of 99.36% and the latter around 96.41% and 87.00%, respectively. Though the LSTM model with attention mechanism enhances precision substantially compared to vanilla LSTMs, they do not reach the same level as Neural ODEs. This discrepancy reflects the precision advantage that Neural ODE’s architecture, with liquid time constant neurons, offers over conventional LSTM structures.

2) *Precision-Recall trade-off:* Flagging benign traffic instances as attacks can prove detrimental in critical real-time systems where user experience or operational efficiency is important. This leads to wastage of resources, degrading Quality of Service (QoS) and most importantly, Denial of Service (DoS) to legitimate requests. The precision discrepancy that Neural ODE (LTC) achieves over conventional LSTM models highlights the minimal rate of false positives. This gives the Neural ODE (LTC) an edge over the other models.

Fig. 3: Precision and recall tradeoff for attack detection

The comparative results are slightly different for recall. Both vanilla LSTM and Neural ODE (LTC) models achieve perfect recall, thus effectively capturing all true positives in the dataset. This high recall performance in both models indicates their proficiency in identifying all positive instances, which is vital in situations where miscalculation of a positive instance can result in serious consequences.

Figure 3 highlights the trade-off between precision and recall across the various models. The LSTM-attention models show a slight decrease in recall. This is due to the trade-off between precision and recall that is often associated with the attention mechanism. The attention mechanism dynamically assigns weights to different parts of the input sequence. Based on data characteristics, the attention mechanism often gets biased towards subtle patterns. The selective focus causes the model to reduce false positive cases, thus improving precision. This nature is inherent in attention mechanisms. On the other hand, the Vanilla LSTM models process the temporal data uniformly, thus avoiding such trade-offs. It can be seen in figure 3 that for vanilla-LSTM models, the precision score is more than that of recall. On the other hand, the Neural ODE (LTC), by virtue of its continuous modeling of intermediate state dynamics, becomes capable of getting a holistic view of past temporal patterns. This is further accentuated by the smoothness achieved by modeling using differential equations. Thus, it is able to capture subtle patterns without reactions to normal variations. This allows the Neural ODE (LTC) to achieve both high precision and recall value. Considering the

F1-score, the Neural ODE (LTC) model again outperforms LSTMs. A high F1-score of 0.9966 for the 36-unit model demonstrates its ability to maintain a high standard across both false positive and false negative rates. While the LSTM model with attention mechanism approaches Neural ODEs in F1- score, particularly with 36 units, they lack the same precision stability seen in Neural ODE (LTC). This suggests that while LSTM-attention models can be a strong alternative for applications requiring balanced performance, Neural ODE models offer a more robust solution in cases where even slight misclassifications are intolerable.

Fig. 4: Precision and model complexity tradeoff

3) *Precision-model complexity tradeoff*: Figure 4 demonstrates a tradeoff between model complexity (number of trainable parameters) and performance (precision). The Neural ODE (LTC) models achieve high precision with fewer parameters. For the vanilla LSTM models, increasing the number of units from 18 to 36 significantly increases the number of trainable parameters, although the precision remains consistent. This indicates diminishing returns in performance for increasing complexity. The LSTM attention model causes an increase in the number of trainable parameters, achieving higher precision compared to its vanilla counterpart. Overall, it is observed that the Neural ODE (LTC) with (18,1) configuration stands out as a strong contender, balancing precision and model complexity. It achieves a higher precision with a number of trainable parameters three times less compared to the LSTM-attention (36 units) model.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper develops method to detect DoW attacks in the serverless Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) paradigm using Neural ODE (LTC) model. Our method outperforms baseline approaches in terms of detection accuracy and precision. The evaluations show that the Neural ODE (LTC) model detects attacks with high precision. This addresses the need to detect attacks in precision critical scenarios where false detections can prove costly, as they may lead to the denial of service for legitimate requests. It also calls off the need for any trade-offs as required for many sequential models, like attention mechanisms. The results demonstrate the robustness

and effectiveness of the proposed method in identifying subtle attack patterns in scenarios where the attack traffic is stealthy and mimics legitimate traffic patterns. This study is limited to the evaluation of a single dataset. Future research will explore distributed denial of wallet attack detection on commercial serverless compute providers and platforms with Neural ODE models.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project SovereignEdge.COGNIT (grant no. 101092711). Additional support was provided by the Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP) funded by Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Garfinkel, "The Cloud Imperative" MIT Technology Review, Oct. 2011 <https://www.technologyreview.com/2011/10/03/190237/the-cloud-imperative> [Accessed: 02-06-2025]
- [2] D. Kelly, E. Barrett, and F. Glavin, "Denial of Wallet: Analysis of a Looming Threat and Novel Solution for Mitigation using Image Classification," University of Galway, Aug. 2023.
- [3] D. Kelly, E. Barret, and F. Glavin, "Denial of wallet—Defining a looming threat to serverless computing," in Journal of Information Security and Applications, Elsevier, Jul. 2021.
- [4] J. Shen, H. Zhang, Y. Geng, J. Li, J. Wang, and M. Xu, "Gringotts: Fast and Accurate Internal Denial-of-Wallet Detection for Serverless Computing," in 2022 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, New York: ACM, Nov. 2022.
- [5] D. Mileski and H. Mihajloska, "Distributed Denial of Wallet Attack on Serverless Pay-as-you-go Model," 2022 30th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR), Belgrade, Serbia, 2022.
- [6] D. Kelly, F. Glavin, and E. Barrett, "DoWTS – Denial-of-Wallet Test Simulator: Synthetic data generation for preemptive defence," Journal of Intelligent Information Systems, vol. 60, Aug. 2022.
- [7] D. Kelly, F. Glavin, and E. Barrett, "DoWNet—classification of Denial-of-Wallet attacks on serverless application traffic," Journal of Cybersecurity, vol. 10, no. 1, Mar. 2024.
- [8] J. Candel, F. Gimeno, and H. Mora, "Generation of a dataset for DoW attack detection in serverless architectures," Data in Brief, vol. 52, Feb. 2024.
- [9] L. Shimol, D. Lavi, E. Klevansky, O. Brodt, D. Mimran, Y. Elovici, A. Shabtai. Detection of compromised functions in a serverless cloud environment, Computers & Security, Vol. 150, 2025.
- [10] P. Renukadevi, S. Amaran, A. Vikram, T. Prabhakara Rao and M. K. Ishak, "Enhancing Cybersecurity Through Fusion of Optimization With Deep Wavelet Neural Networks on Denial of Wallet Attack Detection in Serverless Computing," in IEEE Access, vol. 13, pp. 47111-47122, 2025
- [11] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-term Memory," Neural Computation, MIT-Press, Dec. 1997.
- [12] D. Bahdanau, "Neural machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate" arXiv preprint arXiv, 2014.
- [13] Kyunghyun Cho, Bart van Merriënboer, Caglar Gulcehre, Dzmitry Bahdanau, Fethi Bougares, Holger Schwenk and Yoshua Bengio "Learning Phrase Representations using RNN Encoder-Decoder for Statistical Machine Translation" arXiv preprint arXiv, 2014.
- [14] M. Lechner, R. Hasani, and R. Grosu, "Neuronal Circuit Policies" arXiv, May 2018.
- [15] R. Hasani, M. Lechner, A. Amini, D. Rus, and R. Grosu, "Liquid Time-constant Networks," in Proc of the AAAI, Washington, USA, May 2021.
- [16] K. Funahashi and Y. Nakamura, "Approximation of dynamical systems by continuous time recurrent neural networks," Neural Networks, vol. 6, no. 6, Jan. 1993.
- [17] D.P.Kingma, 2014. "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization" arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980, 2014